

ISic3107

I.Sicily inscription 3107

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Motya

Place of origin (modern)

Mozia

Provenance

Birgi necropolis

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Mozia, Villa Whittaker, inventory 5422

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line

1
: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to

2
: mm

Text

1. [---]Ε,Ις τύ[μβον θε]

2. ντι μῆτ' ἔ[ξάγοντι]

3. ἄνδρα θαν[ό]

4. ντ' ἀγα[θόν]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284789

EDCS 65200113

PHI 329607

PHI 329608

PHI 333758

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